

HEPHAESTUS

Heritage in EuroPe: new tecHnologies in crAft for
prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS

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*Report on craft-technology driven innovation
methodology*

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About HEPHAESTUS

Working across the **regional craft ecosystems** of **Bassano del Grappa (IT)**, **Bornholm (DK)**, **Dals Långed (SE)**, and **Venice (IT)**, the overarching ambition of HEPHAESTUS is *to bring together cutting-edge technologies with traditional craft to co-create solutions in the form of a suite of tools, methodologies, and business models to make the future of European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically sustainable*. HEPHAESTUS will **test and evaluate solutions** co-created across the four regional craft ecosystems within a “**Future of Craft**” **Green Living Lab** situated in Bornholm, a Danish Island and regional municipality given the title of World Craft Region. Ultimately, the project sets out to create a **sustainable network** (especially including regional realities) of heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, local, regional and national authorities, enterprises, and other relevant stakeholders engaged in preservation of craft heritage that will take the project’s results, further adapt and deploy them in a broader range of craft ecosystems, and ensure a long- lasting legacy of the HEPHAESTUS project. The work of HEPHAESTUS is organized around six work packages, each responsible for one specific objective related to the overarching ambition, namely:

Objective 1: Develop new **sustainable business models** for the craft sectors.

Objective 2: Combine **cutting-edge technologies** with craft materials and processes to research and develop new applications and solutions for the digitisation and innovation of the craft sector to improve sustainability and social innovation.

Objective 3: Explore visions for the role of **craft in the future**, integrating emerging technologies and contributing to the circular economy, by engaging craft communities in a participatory ideation process.

Objective 4: Develop a **lifelong learning methodology** and a set of innovative curricula to equip craft-makers with diverse skillsets for innovation.

Objective 5: Establish a **Green Living Lab** for testing the HEPHAESTUS innovations.

Objective 6: To design and operationalise a **bespoke dissemination, communication, and exploitation** strategy.

To achieve these objectives, the consortium includes prominent universities, business schools and a private organization selected for their proven knowledge and expertise on craft heritage, craft materials, and the use of digital technologies and cutting-edge technologies in craft, the proposed innovative and original contributions as well as their trustworthiness. A unique value-added brought to the consortium is represented also by the group of third parties, including craft makers and craft associations, as well as Museums and Municipality representatives, from each of the four regional ecosystems.

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1. Executive Summary

This deliverable presents a framework for a craft-technology-driven innovation methodology that positions digital technologies and cooperative action models as instruments for integrating the New European Bauhaus (NEB) principles, *Beautiful, Sustainable, Together*, into contemporary craft practices. Building on insights from Tasks 1.1-1.2, 2.1, and 3.1, the framework demonstrates how digital and cutting-edge technologies can sustain craft innovation while preserving cultural heritage and promoting inclusivity. Developed collaboratively by FabLab Venezia, CBS, and UNIVE, with contributions from UGOT, the methodology combines conceptual reflection with practical tools, actions, and formats for awareness-raising, experimentation, and lifelong learning.

By aligning technological integration with the NEB values, the framework contributes to re-imagining craft as a driver of ecological transition, social inclusion, and aesthetic experimentation within Europe's creative and cultural ecosystems. It promotes technology as an enabler of awareness and collaboration, valorising traditional practices and fostering innovation rooted in cultural identity and material care. Ultimately, this document provides both a conceptual roadmap and a practical guide for policymakers, educators, and practitioners to advance sustainable, inclusive, and creative transformations in Europe's craft sectors.

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2. Structure of the report and premises

This report sets out to design a craft-driven innovation methodology that integrates cutting-edge technologies with the NEB Bauhaus principles through a design-driven and practice-based approach. The framework positions technology as an enabler of sustainability, inclusivity, and creative renewal. It was developed iteratively through a series of online and in-person workshops with contributions from CBS, UGOT, UNIVE, and FabLab Venezia.

Throughout this document, the term “we” refers to the perspective of FabLab Venezia, which led the methodological development and field experimentation.

The framework is organised around four core dimensions:

- Environmental sustainability – optimising resource use and reducing waste
- Aesthetic and heritage integration – combining traditional know-how with innovation;
- Inclusion and social innovation – enabling new forms of co-creation and access;
- Complexity management – employing parametric and digital tools to streamline production and adaptation.

These dimensions are embedded within the NEB values of Beautiful, Sustainable, and Together, which serve as guiding principles for innovation in the craft sector. Field reflections gathered during the HEPHAESTUS residencies further informed the methodology, highlighting the role of FabLabs and makerspaces as safe, collaborative environments for experimentation, learning, and bottom-up innovation. The resulting framework therefore provides both a conceptual foundation and a practical pathway for positioning crafts at the forefront of Europe’s cultural, social, and ecological transformation.

Structure of the Document

Section 2 introduces the conceptual premises and definitions underpinning the methodology, clarifying what is meant by methodology and technology within this deliverable. It also explains the document’s objectives, its development process, and the NEB values and actors shaping the innovation ecosystem.

Section 3 presents the framework and its four core dimensions: environmental sustainability, aesthetic and heritage integration, inclusion and social innovation, and complexity management.

Section 4 outlines the operational implementation of the methodology through specific actions and formats, supported by reflections from fieldwork and residencies that illustrate its application in practice.

Section 5 discusses how these findings inform policy design and institutional frameworks, proposing recommendations for integrating craft-technology innovation into regional and European policies.

Section 6 concludes by summarising the contribution of the framework and highlighting its implications for future activities within HEPHAESTUS and beyond.

2.1 Definition of Methodology Within this Document

The methodology presented in this document can be defined as an innovation-oriented methodology, designed with a strong emphasis on practical implementation. It proposes ways to create the conditions – and allow others to do so – under which technologies can be more effectively introduced, understood, and adopted within the craft sector.

The operational nature of the methodology derives both from the objectives of the HEPHAESTUS project and from the consolidated experience of the project partners in working with craftspeople, cultural organisations, and technological enablers. It is not limited to producing abstract models or guidelines but rather provides illustrative case-based examples that can guide craftspeople and stakeholders in recognising, testing, and eventually integrating technology in ways that remain coherent with their traditions, skills, and creative practices.

2.2 Definition of Technology Within this Document

Within the framework of this document, the term *technology* is understood primarily in relation to processes of design and production (Scott & Davis, 2007). The focus is therefore not on technology as an abstract or stand-alone innovation, but as a specific set of tools and methods that can directly support and transform the practices of craft making. Emphasis is placed on technologies that intersect with the creative, design, and production phases of craft, where they can act as enablers of new possibilities rather than as replacements of existing skills (Ingold, 2013).

Reference technologies considered in the methodology include 3D scanning, digital modelling, 3D printing, parametric design tools, robotics, and CNC manufacturing techniques. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is also addressed, primarily as a tool that can assist in the design phase, for instance by generating variations, optimising patterns, or supporting the translation of creative ideas into digital forms that can then be materialised (Colombo & Ciuffoletti, 2022).

At the same time, the methodology is not limited to these specific tools. Its purpose is to propose a *modus operandi* – a way of approaching and fostering awareness of technology – that can be applied to a broader spectrum of digital and production tools. This flexibility ensures that the framework remains relevant in a rapidly evolving technological landscape, while still being grounded in concrete examples that resonate with the needs and contexts of the craft sector.

2.3 Description of the Objective – Purpose

The methodology is structured around two main objectives. The first objective is to **support awareness of the opportunities related to the use of technology in craft**. Raising awareness is the essential first step, since many craftspeople may not yet have a clear understanding of what specific tools can offer, how they can be applied, or in which phases of the design and production process they can be most useful. Doing so helps overcome scepticism and the popular image of technology as something that erases or diminishes traditional know-how and manual skills. By repositioning technology as a complementary resource, the methodology demonstrates how digital tools can extend creative capacities and even safeguard heritage, rather than replacing it.

The second objective is to **facilitate the growth of technology-aware practices within craft processes**. This goes beyond immediate adoption, aiming first to build an informed mindset that allows craftspeople to make conscious choices about it and how to integrate digital tools into their work. Doing so provides initial guidance and **suggests entry points to innovation**, offering practical advice on how to access technologies, where to seek support and training, and how to begin experimenting in a manageable and context-sensitive way.

2.4 Development Process of the Framework

In line with the overall approach adopted throughout the HEPHAESTUS project, the framework was developed through an open, participatory, and iterative process that actively involved project partners and, more informally, key stakeholders.

The scope of the methodology, expanding on the intentions outlined in the project proposal, was first agreed upon through online meetings and collaborative work on a shared document among partners. A central point of discussion was that the methodology, and thus the present document, should not be conceived as a step-by-step “how-to” guide for the use of technologies in craft making. Rather, it aims to provide a framework for raising awareness of the potential applications of these technologies and for supporting their effective implementation within the craft sector. The framework was also investigated and refined through some in-person interactions with people beyond the partnership in several occasions such as the workshop in Dås Langed held at Stone Zone in September 2024, the first residencies at FabLab Venezia in 2025, and the dialogues of FabLab Venezia with the local Confartigianato.

The development of this methodology builds directly upon insights from **Task 1.1 (Mapping of regional craft ecosystems)** and **Task 1.2 (Identification of challenges, opportunities, and innovation gaps)**, which provided the socio-cultural and organisational baseline for understanding how technologies can intersect with existing craft traditions. These mappings revealed different levels of technological awareness and local infrastructural capacities, which informed the multi-level structure of the methodology proposed here. The research carried on in work package 1, as also reported in D1.1, frames technology as a perceived urgency linked to some controversies in its implementation linked both to theoretical and operational issues. However, the exploration done with ceramicist Theodore (Theo) Haper Davis propose technology as lively, interesting opportunity to “expand the ways in which craft knowledge is documented, valued, and exhibited”, and the residencies showed that it can also provide new ways in which craft knowledge is produced.

Furthermore, **Task 2.1 (Identification of technologies and innovation potentials)** contributed directly to the present work by outlining the range of digital and production technologies most relevant to the craft sector. The actions and formats proposed in D2.2 translate those findings into an operational framework for implementation and awareness-raising.

Looking ahead, the methodology developed under **Task 2.2** will serve as a bridge toward **Task 3.1 (Speculative design framework)** and **Task 3.2 (Design fictions and participatory ideation)**, which will test and expand it through foresight and design experimentation within the Green Living Lab contexts.

Moreover, relevant connections are present also with WP4 and the lifelong learning methodology and proposition: digital technologies should be incorporated in all the curricula in order to provide at least basic awareness on the potential of cutting-edge processes in craft. The actions and formats in the present document both incorporate specific tools and formats (eg. the podcast as part of T4.2) among the suggested opportunity of learning and offers some further modes to include technological training in craft knowledge at various ages and levels of competency.

Finally, insights and results emerging from this deliverable will be fed into **Task 6.6 (Policy brief and classification framework)**, ensuring that the lessons drawn from field experimentation contribute to evidence-based policymaking for sustainable craft innovation at the European and regional levels.

2.5 NEB values and innovation

The methodology developed within the HEPHAESTUS project is closely aligned with the core values of the NEB Bauhaus (NEB): **Beautiful, Sustainable, Together**. It positions them as guiding principles for fostering innovation in the craft sector.

Beautiful. By supporting awareness of technological opportunities, this methodology encourages the creation of new forms, products, and design languages that remain faithful to the spirit of their time. Technologies such as parametric tools, 3D modelling, or AI-assisted design can expand the aesthetic horizons of craft, enabling practitioners to experiment while maintaining a strong connection to materiality and artisanal skill. In this way, technology becomes a tool for enhancing beauty, not replacing it, reinforcing the role of craft as a source of cultural and creative value.

Sustainable. The methodology contributes to sustainability in both environmental and economic terms. Digital tools allow for prototyping and visualisation before production, reducing material waste, and lowering costs. The integration of sustainable materials, combined with precise and efficient production processes enabled by technologies such as CNC manufacturing or 3D printing, further strengthens this contribution. While many craftspeople already embody sustainable practices in their use of resources, the methodology highlights how technology can amplify these efforts, particularly at the level of small to medium craft enterprises seeking to balance tradition with market competitiveness.

Together. Finally, the methodology places collaboration at the center of technological awareness and innovation. Digital tools and practices often thrive in shared spaces

such as FabLabs, makerspaces, or community workshops, where craftspeople can access resources that might otherwise remain out of reach. These shared environments foster not only the pooling of tools and infrastructures but also the exchange of knowledge and skills among craftspeople, technology providers, and other stakeholders in the wider innovation ecosystem. By enabling both the material and cognitive sharing of resources, the methodology underlines how technology can act as a bridge between different communities, creating conditions for dialogue, co-creation, and collective experimentation.

Regarding **innovation**, particular emphasis is placed on promoting **social innovation** (SI) (Gasparin et al., 2021). Social innovation can be understood as the development and application of novel ideas, practices, and organizational forms that address pressing social needs in more effective, inclusive, and sustainable ways, while simultaneously reshaping social relations and institutional arrangements (Bouchard, 2012; Adams & Hess, 2010). In the case of the involvement of FabLabs, an open, collaborate space for digital fabrication plays a key role in supporting social innovation. By providing access to tools, knowledge, and peer-to-peer learning, FabLabs democratize technological development and foster bottom-up solutions to local challenges, from sustainability initiatives to inclusive entrepreneurship (Smith et al., 2013)

By offering a clear method for exploring and experimenting with digital tools, the methodology lowers barriers to adoption and fosters confidence in the use of new techniques. A key aspect of this approach is the emphasis on “safe spaces”, such as shared workshops, makerspaces, or FabLabs, where experimentation can occur without pressure, mistakes are part of the learning process, and collaboration is encouraged (Sedini et al., 2021). These environments allow craftspeople to test technologies, share knowledge, and gradually integrate new practices into their workflows, facilitating incremental innovation while respecting existing skills and traditions.

To make NEB values actionable, the methodology translates them into a **structured framework** that connects each principle to an operational field and a set of indicative criteria that can be used for design, reflection, or evaluation.

NEB Value	Operational Dimension	Example Indicators / Evaluation Criteria
Beautiful	Aesthetic experimentation grounded in	Evidence of aesthetic innovation using local materials; visible continuity with regional

	material authenticity	identity; integration of traditional craft techniques through digital tools
Sustainable	Environmental and economic responsibility	Optimisation of material use; reduction of waste through digital prototyping; circular use of by-products; balanced combination of handmade and machine-assisted processes
Together	Inclusivity and social innovation	Diversity of actors involved in projects; accessibility of tools and spaces; inclusion of marginalised or younger groups; presence of co-creation, mentoring, and shared learning practices

These indicators are **not prescriptive**, but serve as **evaluative lenses** for analysing the impact of technological integration on the aesthetic, ecological, and social dimensions of craft innovation. They ensure coherence with the **NEB Bauhaus Compass (2023)** and with HEPHAESTUS’s ambition to align craft-based experimentation with Europe’s cultural, environmental, and social transition agendas.

2.6 The actors in the innovation ecosystem

Effective innovation in the craft sector is rarely the result of isolated efforts. Rather, it emerges from shared engagement among multiple actors, each contributing to the creation of a thriving environment for experimentation, learning, and adoption of new technologies. To achieve meaningful technological awareness and integration, coordinated action is required at different levels – from policy frameworks and educational programs to bottom-up initiatives and peer-to-peer knowledge sharing (Temeltas, H., & Kaya, C., 2021).

The methodology therefore seeks to envision the role of the full spectrum of actors involved in the innovation ecosystem in fostering technology adoption and awareness. In the next section, the actors are described in more detail.

Craft associations and business support organizations provide networks, advocacy, and resources that facilitate access to technologies and training opportunities. They act as intermediaries between individual craftspeople and other innovation actors, helping to disseminate best practices and build trust in new methods. Within the Italian context and specifically in the Veneto region the main involved organizations are the Confartigianato and CNA, with their relative fields of action and offices for geographical jurisdiction.

Innovation providers (FabLabs, consultants, technology hubs) supply the tools, infrastructure, and expertise necessary for hands-on experimentation. By offering shared spaces and guidance, they enable craftspeople to explore technologies safely, test prototypes, and co-develop solutions collaboratively. From secondary education to universities and lifelong learning programs, educational actors play a key role in building foundational knowledge and digital literacy. They introduce craft students to technology-enabled processes early in their training and provide continuous professional development for practitioners seeking to expand their skill sets.

Policy makers design and implement supportive policies, funding programs, and regulatory frameworks that create the conditions for technology adoption to flourish. Their role ensures that innovation is sustainable, accessible, and aligned with broader cultural and economic goals.

Craft makers, artisans, and craft companies are central to the ecosystem, these practitioners can be categorized into three groups:

- Early adopters: Already implementing technologies and able to act as peer mentors.
- Aware but hesitant: Understand the possibilities but are not yet ready to adopt.
- Not yet aware: Unfamiliar with technological opportunities.

3. The framework

Aesthetics, sustainability and a certain necessity of innovation have always been integral to craft work. Nevertheless, craft practices are facing nowadays struggles to be adequately valorised in the market and to be appealing to younger generations (Partarakis et al., 2025). This document proposes a conceptual but also operational framework of how craft and NEB principles can come together in a fair and contemporary way, using technologies. Using **contemporary digital tools to represent emerging and traditional aesthetics, to reinforce the importance of sustainability and to build new ways of working together**, may give craft new opportunities to grow and generate interest in an increasing number of younger people and future professionals.

The framework is based on four core dimensions, that integrate the NEB principles (beautiful, sustainable, together). These four dimensions are: **1. Environmental sustainability, 2. Aesthetic and heritage integration, 3. Inclusivity and social**

innovation, and 4. Complexity Management (Figure 6). These dimensions highlight the opportunities offered by digital technologies to enhance the creative, competitive and social potential of craft production, while staying true to the craft makers and craft enterprise traditional values and specificity and eventually helping the preservation and transmission of traditional knowledge and skills. The following sections will outline the four dimensions in detail.

3.1 Environmental Sustainability

While **sustainability has always been somehow intrinsically tied to craft** (the use of sustainable and nature based-materials, the production in relatively small batches, the attention to waste and how to minimize it also for economic reasons) (Yair, 2010), the use of digital technology can give it **new connotations**, in parallel to existing good practices.

The possibility of **3D modelling and virtual prototyping**, rendering and visualization can be a help during the ideation process. Before the physical production of prototypes, a wider variety of options can be evaluated on screen. This, of course, is most likely tied to certain type of craft production: for example, those happening in bigger enterprises or aimed at designing furniture and complements. Similarly, dealing with objects and shapes in a virtual mode can help compute the number of resources that are needed to produce certain numbers or, in case of CNC (Computer Numerical Control) production processes, can optimize materials consumption (Li et al., 2019).

Digital fabrication processes are very compatible with the **use of natural or bio based materials**: 3D printing can be done with clay, biopolymers such as PLA (polylactic acid) which is biodegradable in small parts, BHA, which is soluble in water (Rojas-González et al., 2023) and an increasing number of composite materials that use both natural waste (e.g., coffee grounds, orange peels, cork powder) and manufacturing waste (e.g., marble powder, acrylic, discarded 3D prints themselves) a source (Mansingh et al., 2023; Scaffaro et al., 2021). Laser cutting processes can be done on paper, wood, fabric, other natural materials. Of course, the use of digital technology is not more sustainable per se, a responsible approach to it should be trained and supported (Nazir et al., 2023).

Technological innovation for sustainability relates also to the development of new processes to recycle or reuse some waste material (see [WP5 Kiln project as Living Lab Activity](#): the innovation does not lie in the use of advanced technologies but in the

set-up of a new process). **Casting processes** (Figure 1) can greatly benefit from digital fabrication processes as the same positive, particularly in virtual form, can be reproduced and serve for more than one casting (Bassoli et al., 2007).

Figure 1: Scanning process and casting supports for the reproduction of an elephant figure in bronze with lost wax process (work and photos FabLab Venezia)

3.2 Aesthetic and Heritage Integration

Technology enables new form of creative research, but also the exact registration and transmission of ancient forms through digitization and digital archiving. In this sense it can serve both as a tool to explore different aesthetics that could not be achieved with analogue instruments, and it makes visual data and information available to a wider public. For example, as we see in the work of [Andrea Salvatori](#) who uses ceramic 3D printing (Figure 2) establishing a sort of dialogue with the machine, an informed use of technology can lead to unexpected, aesthetically intriguing but also very “honest” outcomes. Salvatori works simultaneously with the machine, going beyond just defining a 3D model to be reproduced but interacting with the digitized production process with his human input. The outcome maintains a character of unpredictability and surely a craft value.

Figure 2: Andrea Salvatori and the Ikebana Rock and roll project. Photos by Wasp

During the first FabLab HEPHAESTUS residencies, the three Swedish craft makers have all investigated the aesthetic implications of using 3D scanning and 3D printing in the research, with a particular interest in twisting the processes, harnessing the errors or finding the limits of technologies. Lukas Arons decided to investigate the notion of skin and 3D printing and the features of the layers, enlarging them, replicating them, printing and casting. The layer, and the possibility to show it instead of hiding it as an unwanted though unavoidable byproduct of the 3D printing process is an example of the new aesthetic questions and topics that may arise as an opportunity from the use of digital fabrication technologies in (artistic) craft.

Figure 3: Lukas' work on the "skin" during the FabLab HEPHAESTUS residencies in 2025. Photos by D20

The digitization of objects, artworks, historical items, whether through 2D or 3D scanning, represents an unprecedented possibility for exploration and circulation of visual knowledge, material processing and exploration of ancient craft objects. The research project developed by UNIVE on some ceramics from the Musei Civici of Bassano, that have been reproduced digitally and physically with a gamified context, provide the younger generations and interactive and engaging medium for discovery.

Big cultural institutions as the British Museums and the Rijksmuseum in Amsterdam have put consistent effort in making part of the collections available online, with high resolution pictures and 3D models for download, to foster heritage knowledge and possibly creative remixes, an educational activity based on the elaboration of existing items to produce creative outcomes while familiarizing with certain artistic and historical objects.

Figure 4: Collection of downloadable 3D models from the British Museum profile on Sketchfab.

3.3 Inclusion and Social Innovation

Inclusivity represents both a value and a methodological approach. In line with the NEB principle Together, this dimension focuses on how innovation processes can make craft accessible to wider participation and shared learning. Digital and collaborative environments, such as FabLabs and community workshops, are understood as enablers of peer-to-peer learning, collective experimentation, and mutual support (Oppedisano, 2024). This dimension underscores the social dimension of craft as a vehicle for cohesion, exchange, and empowerment, positioning collaborative making as a driver of social innovation and civic engagement within local ecosystems (Jones et al., 2021).

Cooperation and inclusion within tech-related craft processes can be meant in two ways: first, it works as an opportunity for new collaboration among crafters, artisans and innovators, and new business models, and second, as a driver of social innovation (Gasparin et al., 2021).

The arrival of digital fabrication technologies in craft is translating to a necessity of cooperation among artisans, that are very seldom willing to learn how to use digital technology themselves, and innovation providers. This, however, is not a negative occurrence it, instead, promotes a fertile exchange among different professionals, may foster the growth of new jobs and ultimately replicates a type of relationship which is already present in the craft world. For example, when artists need to rely on foundries to produce an artwork in bronze. Foundries are indeed one of the realms that are showing the greater interest and use of digital fabrication processes. More and more often the artist does not provide an adequate positive for the casting, particularly in terms of dimensions. The small-scale draft can be scanned, digitally scaled and possibly edited, 3D printed and used by the foundry, the level of detail and fidelity can be outstanding and, as stated above, a 3D model remains for future necessities. Other types of collaborations between artisans and technology providers can happen, both in relation to the creative and artistic research and just for the production phase. Meanwhile, technology can be a driver of social innovation because:

- It introduces a new set of tools that may be more appealing to younger generations and that can be used in craft production (Gandini & Gerosa, 2023). The dialogue between craft and technology can and should be fostered in schools in a playful (ludic) way, to help regain interest and confidence in using the hands together with digital tools. It should of course also be emphasized in design universities and academia to showcase new creative possibilities.

- Digital fabrication technologies can be learned in a relatively easy way, as they do not require a specific educational background and can serve as a means of integrating new or reskilling “old” workers in the craft ecosystems: some experimentations have been successfully conducted by [Association Nuovo Incanto](#) (Zernitz, 2025) in Venice, fostering the employment of migrant people in local craft enterprises and ateliers, meanwhile, FabLab Venezia has trained some younger people on 3D modelling who then have been employed by a Venetian stone working enterprise and a senior worker from a glass making enterprise has been mentored and reskilled to use new 3D and parametric modelling in order not to lose his work and, instead, gain a new position within the enterprise.
- Thanks to digital fabrication technologies, it is easier to prototype and produce objects following a logic of mass customization or based on individual needs. This is particularly relevant for addressing the necessities of people with disabilities or for producing small batches that serve specific groups. For example, Studio Boey’s haptic cooking ware, developed for blind people, was first prototyped using 3D printing and then produced by craft makers (Studio Boey, 2024) (Figure 5). As stated before, craftsmanship is often tied to small-scale production, but the possibility of having digitized data makes one-of-a-kind, highly personalized production possible.

Figure 5: Haptics of Cooking, Studio Boey Wang. This bespoke measuring cup has small holes, when blocked with a fingertip, the user can feel when the liquid volume reaches a specific level. Via DesignWanted

3.4 Complexity Management

The fourth dimension concerns the capacity of crafts to engage with increasing levels of design and production complexity through digital and parametric tools. Rather than promoting standardisation, this dimension focuses on maintaining adaptability and responsiveness. This can be used for aesthetics and formal research but also for management and communication purposes.

Parametric design is a form of 3D modelling and design that enables the development of intricate forms, unprecedented design and virtually infinite variety of shapes based on input parameters (instead of “static” 3D modelled shapes). New forms of craft can rise from mastering these types of tools and, while the debate may be on to what extent this may be defined craft, traditional craft enterprises are already using this software. For example, FabLab Venezia supported one of the main glass making enterprises in Murano by teaching one of the employees how to classify, edit and manage the many

pieces that compose the very famous chandeliers, which somehow already embed an analogic parametric approach in their production.

Parallely, it is important to note that digital can be an important help in more trivial tasks such as administration and for communication and competitiveness. Training the craft makers' capacity to understand and embrace digital technologies should result also in their increased capacity to trust software particularly for those less motivating, creativity and practice related tasks. This way, more time could be dedicated to research, production, experimentation. Lastly, within the scope an aim of this document, also AI can be included in this enumeration. It should be known and explored in order to understand if and how it could be useful for certain activities, particularly with the goal of relieving from some tiring or complex tasks or potentially to provide inputs.

Craft-Technology Innovation Framework

Figure 6: The Craft-Technology Innovation Framework

The aforementioned values form part of an evidence-based framework, that also draws upon the experience of FabLab Venezia and its peers. To translate it into a beneficial attitude for the end users, the craft makers, it should be transmitted in informal contexts and with production-based formats, to avoid theory-driven positions and possibly allow for changes, refinements, to better adapt to the real ecosystem necessities.

4. Suggestions for implementation

This chapter proposes potential operational steps that can be used to implement and investigate the framework with crafts makers in real life.

4.1 Characteristics

The proposed framework grounds itself in the evidence that a practice- and example-based approach is particularly beneficial to provide craft makers with concrete, valuable and useful opportunities to amplify their interest in technology and learn. The following characteristics and values, that inform the subsequent definition of actions and formats that can be used to implement the methodology, provide an overview of the 'hows' and 'whys', hinting to possible controversies and solutions, that may arise in the process of bringing innovation to life in tradition-oriented environments.

Practice as a value

Practice, as the moment of actively doing things, both when making a final product and when experimenting or trying, needs to stay at the core of the methodology. The language of craft making is strongly tied to actions, materials, and physical effort (Sennet, 2008): an innovation of dialogue only aimed at theoretical thought, without implications on the act of making, would not be well received. Vice versa, a dialogue based on examples, trials and errors, and the possibility to touch with your hands, may spark interest and help overcome perceived distance and skepticism (Roy & Sarkar, 2024).

The stance on authenticity and respect of tradition vs. tech evangelization

In order to build a place of trust and willingness to get to know technology, it is important to make it clear that digital tools (particularly within the scope of this methodology) should not be meant and used as a way to substitute traditional craft skills and valuable immaterial heritage. On the contrary, they can be very helpful in

providing help on boring, hard or lower value tasks, while potentially expanding creative research.

Moreover, some seem to fear a potential threat of standardization linked to the use of technology (Neufeind, O'Reilly, & Ranft, 2018). While this could be true, if technology is precisely used for that purpose, new tools can also be the door for the expansion of personal style and research (Kroezen et al., 2021). Through awareness-rising and learning, each person is invited to build a personal path of relationship with technology, deciding whether to use it, or not, externalize the process or master it.

There is also the possibility of a new authenticity of contemporary craft, that is carried out through a deep knowledge of the processes and the machine functioning and leads to the valorization of what a tech-aided production is or is not and what a machine can or cannot do. A clear example is provided by the development of objects that are produced using 3D printing and where the layers (that constitute the visible characteristics of how the technology works) are not hidden but instead become part of the form and the output.

The “rejection” or “fear” of innovation

One of the main difficulties we can encounter while proposing digital fabrication processes and technologies to craft practitioners is the strong resistance to even a first contact due to sentiments of fear and mistrust. It often stems from the current representation of tech in media, that proposes technology both as a lifesaver not to be missed and a threatening force that can be stronger than us. There is a lack of spaces where technology is explained honestly, through relatable examples and with the aim to provide understating and empower. Providing occasions for honest discussion among different actors, opportunities for mutual learning and even playful interaction can help demystify the vision of technology as an unavoidable, bad force. It can be managed and used to the crafts' advantage, once people can use it knowingly.

4.2 Actions and formats

With the aim to make the methodology accessible and replicable, we decided to depict a set of actions and formats that acknowledge the possible different levels of awareness, commitment, interest and capacity of investment of craft makers and enterprises.

Action 1: raise awareness

Objective: to overcome resistances and make tech something more familiar, to showcase possibilities.

Awareness-rising can be pursued through different means and media:

- collective learning and exchange occasions (talks, informal roundtables)
- awareness campaigns (e.g., social, newsletters, articles...) by the institutions /associations
- establishment of places where you can see examples and tech in action (out of formal and institutional environments)
- provide really accessible and practical online/offline resources (e.g., photos, factsheets, podcast)

The goal should be to create a coherent cultural environment where digital technologies are “domesticated” and seen as accessible and potentially, while providing opportunities to see how they work in person. These actions require lower commitment and are meant to be an entry-level opportunity for everyone. Given the relatively low cost of the actions, they can be implemented quite easily also as a starting trial and can become structural with time. Cooperation among associations and support organizations and innovation providers is crucial, unless organizations have already implemented innovation protocols within their structure and are trained on tools and processes.

Examples of formats

1A) Short group talk/training: 1-2 hours, for groups of artisans, based on showing and explaining case studies with a focus on materials, processes, operational issues and potential. It provides concrete examples they can relate to, helps overcome fear and mistrust. A similar format can be done also for the representatives of associations/policy makers/institutions, in order to provide inspirational examples and educate on the results that can be achieved with purposeful innovation.

1B) The podcasts: HEPHAESTUS podcast program (T4.2) is an example of a practical way to provide valuable knowledge in an informal way, so that those who are interested can deepen their knowledge in other ways.

Action 2: support free experimentation both for entry level and for the more proficient

Objective: allow to understand through making, possibly “try before buy”, to explore in a protected way without conspicuous commitment, to validate possible solutions future cooperation with innovation providers.

- supported programs for residencies
- practical workshops where to learn by doing

Examples of formats

2A) Residency program for entry level knowledge of technology: two weeks can be enough to produce a prototype on some specific topic or process they decided to investigate. It requires fundings and the constant presence of a tutor (who can follow 2-3 people). If adequately designed, it provides immediate insights and an immersive opportunity to try without pressure. It has proved to foster the craft makers' trust and positive opinion on technology, even if they decide not to use it systematically. A second HEPHAESTUS residency program (T2.3) is planned for March/April 2026.

2B) Residency program for autonomous/experts in tech: to be held in equipped spaces, it can provide free space and equipment to experiment and should last two weeks to one month or two. The focus here should be on how to nurture the growth of such spaces. It is important to notice that also among the craft makers or enterprises that have decided to use technology for certain processes, only a very small amount will buy the technology, meaning that in an increasing innovative ecosystem, the role of innovation spaces will remain crucial.

2C) Short workshops: a very topic-bound opportunity that aims at exploring a specific tool or process through a practical approach, typically for those who have already some experiences with technology. It can be particularly interesting for neo craft practitioners, students, and young professionals.

Action 3: foster deeper knowledge and Lifelong Learning (LLL)

Objective: provide professional training for those who decide to invest in knowing and owning technology, for bigger companies that have the structure to invest. The action can take advantage of what already exists at a local level and beyond, focusing on granting access to resources and opportunities:

- facilitate access to existing resources (grants, fundings, online and offline training)
- support local structures and spaces that offer courses and services and/or seek ways to ensure those services are free/low cost.

Examples of formats

3A) Training course: a longer format (24+ hours), can be funded through regional funds and developed cooperatively between institutions and innovators. Usually, participants are already motivated and aware, should nevertheless have a practical approach and

provide operational knowledge (although a general one and not tailored to the specific use case).

3B) 1:1 consultancy: a safe space where artisans are more prone to engage and share information on their specific use cases. It can be more general or practical if it is not financed through specific programs; it can be expensive and not accessible.

Action 4: aim at systemic innovation

Objective: build an environment that fosters collaboration, innovation and interest in craft practices beyond the craft making itself.

Two of the main aspects would be:

- valorize joint technical and craft training in schools, at different levels. places such as FabLabs and maker spaces have always put strong in offering learning opportunities that merge technological tools and the values of making, creativity, personalization and manual skills. Nowadays it is proving to be increasingly important to promote analogical skills in people of younger age, who are instead very rapid at learning tech-related skills (Rayna & Striukova, 2021).
- cooperation between cultural institutions and innovators: an effective way to work towards an overall innovative arts and craft ecosystem is promoting collaboration or at least mutual knowledge among innovators and institutions.

Examples of formats

4A) Specific programs in schools. This topic exceeds the scope of the present methodology, however both shorter formats would be a first step toward formalized learning programs and subjects (as the Swedish slojd education).

4B) Finance/promote stable cooperation among places of culture that host “traditional” residencies and artistic activities and innovation places (e.g. FabLab Venezia has some protocols or established practices with local museums and the Culture department of the municipality).

Figure 7: diagram showing proposed formats in relation to users' awareness and willingness of investment

Figure 8: difficulty of implementation of proposed formats (in terms of effort of organizations involved and requirement of policy change)

4.2.2 The methodology in action: field reflections during the residencies

The interaction between FabLab Venezia and the craft makers during the February 2025 residences has served as an in-progress validation of certain actions and values proposed in the methodology. FabLab Venezia tried to provide a judgment-free, informal space for experimentation and confrontation. Rob Curran, Linnea Dalstrand and Lukas Arons (HEPHAESTUS craft ambassadors) have shared their perspective on the residency experience, including the mentorship provided, the structure and timing and would be needed to foster the use of technology in craft in other contexts.

Some excerpts of the final conversation:

Speaker 1: *“I won't go home and buy a 3D printer, but maybe in a year or so, I know that I've experienced this, and I have some idea of what I can do. And perhaps at that point, it's like, okay, maybe I could employ this technology to help me with something.”*

Speaker 2: *“...maybe it's not something that I would work on directly, but I think it's very useful. And it has been some time. Yes, and I think I learned a lot. And yes, and a lot of ideas, which is fun. (...) it's starting to grow other stuff in my mind as well. That's beautiful, (...) because I'm interested in decor in some ways, and yes, I think that's developed something in my mind, which I think is very useful.”*

Speaker 2: *“It's also interesting because I have been working in the same way as I worked before, but now I'm taking stuff out of the computer and mirror them in the real world.”*

Speaker 4: *“Yes, the process is kind of the same, I realized. But also putting this out of the computer and then take a picture of them and put it in the computer and then make images of these ones in the computer and then place them out again. It's an interesting process for me. Otherwise, I would have done all of this in the computer. But it's a little bit what Rob is doing with the in and out, and in again and out again. Print, and then you put it in, you scan it again, print, in, computer, out.”*

Speaker 3: *“Personally, I think the difficult part is that it's the tool that I cannot deal with myself. So, I must have help with that tool. And that's both the digital part, but also the printing part, because it's a technique of itself, you need a lot of knowledge to make it work well. So, it's the kind of tool that you, it's like when you cast it in bronze, you give the model to the foundry, and you get it back in bronze. (...) And in that sense I can see possibilities.”*

Speaker 3: *“But the idea of having a residence place is, of course, very interesting, I think, because a lot of people maybe want to work with it, but they have no way how to do it. The thing is that, like me, who had no experience at all, I really need to lean on Leo (one of the FabLab’s founders-Authors’s note) to get something done at all. Otherwise, I would have been sitting here like, okay, and now what? So, this connection (between resident and mentor-Authors’s note) is very important in this residency thing.”*

Alberta asks: *“would it be interesting for such spaces to be formalized in every, I don’t know, in every place where craftsmanship happens? Like, would it be beneficial to have laboratories like this where you have people that can help you work on this, work with technology, experiment?”*

Speaker 1: *“maybe it’s not knowing what is feasible with a space like this. I mean, maybe there’s a bit of, for me, I don’t know the limitations. I know that maker spaces produce certain things. So, I have that image of what’s possible. And, maybe it’s difficult for me to see how it can work for me if I want it*

Speaker 3: *“would it have changed if we would have had a couple of weeks before we came here, like a one hour conference about the thing, would it have changed our idea when we came? I’m not sure. I’m not sure, no.”*

Speaker 1: *“I think we probably would use that information, but I don’t know if I’m really engaged with that kind of thing. I kind of need to see the thing move and touch and smell and all that kind of thing. I think me personally, I’m quite like that.”*

5. Towards policy making

5.1 The role of the actors

Each one of the actors constitutes a relevant piece for the implementation of the methodology, as the actuation of the proposed actions entails collaborations at different levels. The methodology hints also at some strategic suggestions for policy making, that fall beyond the scope of the present document, which have emerged during various conversations with the actors and as a result of the everyday innovation practice of FabLab Venezia.

Particularly, it should be underlined that the dialogue among innovation providers, such as FabLabs and makerspaces, and the business support organizations and sector associations enhances the possibility to organize and implement more meaningful training occasions for the end users and beneficiaries. Support organizations often have access to fundings that are used to organize courses, workshops and consultancies (García-Ruiz & Lena-Acebo, 2022). To design adequate training programs a collaboration among the organizations, the innovators that have a deeper knowledge of the market and of the technological advancements and the academic institutions that can provide some solid backgrounds, is desirable. Providing spaces at institutional level to gather the end users' perceived necessities and learning desires is also important.

The whole methodology is strongly based on a bottom-up approach as a catalyst for change. Indeed, bottom-up experimentation can provide valuable data and experiences for policymaking level decisions (Sabatier, 1986).

Policies are, then, fundamental to achieving widespread innovation, making new approaches systemic and providing actors such as schools and other public and private entities capable of being informed players within the system. This also involves place-making and the necessity of having accessible open spaces where to learn and access technology. This is one of the main issues that are generally reported by end users in relation to the possibility of making innovation real in their practices (UNESCO, 2021). Once more, FabLabs and makerspaces action models could be a relevant starting point to understand what works and good practices can be replicated in other ecosystems.

FabLabs have proven to be relevant spaces for community building and for multidisciplinary and multilevel interaction: a place where organization, institution representatives, citizen and creative people come together in an informal way, potentially building new business/social relations.

Figure 9: diagram of relations for an innovative ecosystem with innovation spaces at the core. Black lines describe traditional interactions, green ones suggest new, technology-related, possibly generative interactions. Elaboration FabLab Venezia 2024

5.2 Policy hints

The methodological framework presented in this deliverable also holds implications for **policy design and funding structures** at both the European and regional levels. By framing *making* as a mode of innovation aligned with the **NEB Bauhaus** principles - *Beautiful, Sustainable, Together* - the methodology supports the translation of local craft practices into broader policy and economic ecosystems.

In particular, it draws on insights regarding the role of hybrid spaces - such as shared studios, FabLabs, and makerspaces - which act as bridges between traditional artisans and new technologies, fostering innovation, transmission of knowledge, and inclusive participation in making practices. These environments blend manual and digital knowledge, promote inclusive and experiential learning, and sustain local innovation through *embodied knowledge transmission*.

However, as the policy brief underlines, such spaces often face **insufficient recognition and structural support**. The following recommendations derive directly from that analysis and from the findings of the present deliverable:

- **Recognise FabLabs, makerspaces, and community craft hubs as formal actors in Europe’s craft and innovation ecosystem**, integrating them into cultural, industrial, and educational policy frameworks.
- **Provide targeted EU and regional support** for their infrastructure, technical staffing, and training activities, ensuring their long-term sustainability.
- **Embed ‘Making Places’ in Smart Specialisation and regional innovation strategies** as physical and social infrastructures that connect NEB values with local economic development.
- **Link such hybrid innovation spaces to lifelong learning and vocational training schemes**, addressing the reduced visibility and perceived value of crafts as viable educational and career options.

By reinforcing these “making infrastructures,” policymakers can tackle two interrelated challenges identified through this methodology:

- (1) the **fragility of the physical and institutional infrastructure** supporting craft innovation; and
- (2) the **difficulty of intergenerational transmission** of craft knowledge.

The framework calls for a renewed relationship between crafting and technology in schools. Similarly to the Swedish sloyd concept, and the way it is incorporated throughout education, craft can gain a more relevant role in school education (Hansson & von Busch, 2023; Thorbjörnsson, 2006). A craft education strategy should be put in place, that is able to connect meaningfully more manual activities to contemporary digital education. Universities, arts academies and other tertiary education institutions should either reinforce craft related knowledge (faculties of design) or support the teaching digital tools besides the more analog ones.

Ultimately, the policy relevance of this methodology lies in demonstrating how bottom-up experimentation and hybrid innovation spaces can inform top-down frameworks for **sustainable and inclusive regional development**, in line with the **NEB Bauhaus Compass** and **EU transition pathways for cultural and creative industries**.

6. Conclusion

This deliverable has presented a framework for a craft-technology driven innovation methodology that integrates the **NEB Bauhaus (NEB)** values of Beautiful, Sustainable, and Together into the future development of the craft sector. The methodology positions technology not as a substitute for traditional skills, but as an enabler of continuity, learning, and collaboration across craft ecosystems.

By translating NEB principles into operational dimensions, such as environmental sustainability, aesthetics and heritage integration, and inclusivity, the methodology provides **a coherent structure to guide experimentation, training, and policy development**. It invites a view of innovation that is deeply material, socially engaged, and culturally situated, strengthening the contribution of craft to Europe’s green and digital transitions.

Beyond a descriptive model, the methodology acts as a practical and reflective tool: it can support local actors, educators, and policymakers in fostering environments where experimentation and tradition coexist productively (Sgorla et al., 2025). It also highlights the strategic importance of “**places of making**”—FabLabs, shared studios, and community workshops—as infrastructures for innovation and transmission, in line with current European cultural and industrial agendas. In summary, the proposed approach redefines innovation in craft as a process of making with awareness: of materials and environments, of people and relations, of heritage and change. It offers a foundation for future actions and collaborations aimed at sustaining craft as both a cultural legacy and a driver of inclusive, sustainable, and beautiful futures.

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